

On the performance of a deep learning-based anomaly detection system for 5G mobile networks

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Abstract—Cybersecurity defense systems have evolved, in fact, new intrusion detection systems (IDS) allows to identify cyber-threats that may have only recently gone unnoticed. However, new protection challenges are raised by the new upcoming fifth generation (5G) mobile technology. The new advanced features of 5G will make that existing detection procedures become obsolete in case they are not adapted accordingly. This paper propose a 5G-oriented architecture to efficiently and quickly conduct the analysis of network flows to identify cyber-threats in 5G mobile networks, by making use of deep learning techniques. Intensive experiments are also included so as to analyze the robustness of the proposed inspection capabilities as well as to determine how many network flows, gathered from 5G subscribers' User Equipments (UE), we can inspect in real-time.

I. INTRODUCTION AND MOTIVATION

Cybersecurity researchers and professionals have designed and developed various defense systems that protect mobile devices, computers and networks from hackers want to intrude on a system with malicious intention. These defense systems address cybersecurity threats, including virus, Trojans, worms, and botnets. The solutions include proactive approaches that anticipate and remove vulnerabilities in the system, and reactive approaches such as intrusion detection systems (IDS). However, these approaches need to adapt and evolve to new technologies and communication networks facing new cyber-threats.

Any protection mechanism, such as the ones based on IDS, needs to operate by integrating algorithms with good and precise detection capabilities, allowing them quick data processing gathered by information sources. Without these capabilities, IDSs cannot perform their monitoring and analysis functions in real time, making it almost impossible to detect potential cyber-attacks. This problem is because current networks provide increasingly high transmission rates, going in a few years from 100 Mbps to the current data rate of 10 Gbps in wired networks. Large volumes of information flowing through networks make IDSs ineffective to gather and analyze every network packet. As an example, Deep Packet Inspection (DPI) tools like Snort [1] can properly work on wired networks up to 1 Gbps, starting to discard packets due to overhead from 1.5 Gbps [2]. In order to improve performance, many works are focused on advanced parallelization techniques based on hardware accelerators. Among them, techniques based on Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) support speeds of

up to 4 Gbps without loss [3], while the ones based on Application-Specific Integrated Circuit (ASIC) reach speeds close to 7.2 Gbps [4].

Due to the increase of bandwidth, IDS-based solutions making deep analysis were forced to evolve toward new ways of detection, moving from inspecting raw network packets to analyzing traffic network flows with innovative AI-based techniques [5]. For example, a Block-Based Neural Network (BBNN) for an anomaly-based IDS achieved around 22 Gbps throughput by using an FPGA architecture [6], in which a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to reduce data dimensionality was also proposed. In this context, a complete survey is focused on solutions to quickly classify collected network flows to detect attacks or malicious code [7]. Nonetheless, these solutions appear to be insufficient in the coming years, since networks with even higher transmission speeds are predicted. Currently, a huge promotional effort is being made to raise the new upcoming fifth generation (5G) mobile technology. The new advanced features of 5G will make that existing detection procedures become obsolete in case they are not adapted accordingly.

The 5G-PPP consortium has identified a pool of Key Performance Indicators (KPI) [8] that have a high impact when analyzing and inspecting traffic network flows. It needs to determine certain characteristics of the incoming network flow in an efficient and quick way so as to detection procedures are a success. Among these KPIs, we next highlight four of them that make detection procedures an even greater challenge in 5G mobile networks.

- 1000 times higher mobile data volume per geographical area.
- 10 to 100 times more connected devices.
- 10 times to 100 times higher typical user data rate.
- End-to-End latency of <1ms.

As shown, the large number of User Equipments (UE) belonging to 5G subscribers, the large volumes of traffic data produced by them, as well as the reduced latency in connectivity makes us face new challenges to be solved without losing detection accuracy in real-time scenarios. Our contribution with the article at hand is the proposal of a 5G-oriented architecture to efficiently and quickly conduct the analysis of network flows to identify cyber-threats in 5G

Fig. 1. Network Anomaly Detection System.

mobile networks, by making use of deep learning techniques. Intensive experiments are also included so as to analyze the robustness of the proposed inspection capabilities as well as to determine how many network flows, gathered from 5G subscribers' UEs, we can inspect in real-time.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. In Section II, we outline the proposed architecture for inspecting network flows in 5G mobile networks, detailing the features extracted from such network flows and the inspection techniques based on deep learning used. Section III shows the intensive experiments conducted to demonstrate the feasibility of our proposal, while conclusions and future work are finally drawn in Section IV.

II. PROPOSAL FOR NETWORK ANOMALY DETECTION IN 5G

Our proposal provides a network anomaly detection system integrated into 5G architecture. Therefore, following we present how our system is distributed and interact with other elements in 5G networks, as well as what network flow features and deep learning based techniques are used.

A. Architecture for network inspection

5G networks are conceived as extremely flexible infrastructures based on an architecture organized by functional planes that provides separation of concerns to simplify and address the complete system requirements. Among these planes, we propose a high-level design of the management and orchestration plane closely follows the ETSI NFV architecture [9] that have also been used as basis by other proposals [10], [11]. The architecture, as shown in Figure 2, consists of four groups of components: Virtualized Infrastructure (VI); Virtualized Network Functions (VNFs); Management and Orchestration (MANO); and Operations and Business Support Systems (OSS/BSS). The VI group virtualizes the physical resources (computing, storage, and network) and exposes them for consumption by VNFs. The MANO group manages the combination of VNFs implementing network services, the full life cycle of VNFs, the deployment of VNFs into virtualized resources, and the network slicing for supporting multi-tenancy. MANO controls the general behavior of the infrastructure considering the policy set defined by Virtual Network Operators (VNO) of the OSS/BSS.

Fig. 2. High-level management and orchestration plane.

Among these policies, the VNO must define security policies to be applied to network resources under its control. The Security Policy Manager module considers these security policies and takes best actions after evaluating the input provided by the Monitoring and Analytics module. This module must process current monitoring information generated by network resources and identify the causes from any anomaly detected. In order to achieve effective network anomaly detection, we propose the system, depicted in the Figure 1, composed of virtualized components with two functions: anomaly symptom detection and network anomaly detection. The first one is located in radio access network (RAN) infrastructure and focused on the fast search of anomaly symptom, i.e. any trace or sign of anomaly in the network traffic generated by User Equipments (UE) connected to RAN. The second one is a collector of symptoms timestamped and RAN geo-located, where a central process analyses the timeline and the relation of these symptoms to identify any network anomaly. When an anomaly is found, it is immediately communicated to the Monitoring and Analytics module.

In addition, our system proposes the use of flow analysis as technical mechanism extracting anomaly symptoms from network traffic. Although, applying deep packet inspection (DPI) permits to look deep into the L2/3 flows, even identifying specific applications, it could be too resource consuming considering 5G mobile data volume. Therefore, the instantiation

of DPI-based mechanism may be deployed in particular cases for specific events or policy actions (e.g. after a detection of botnet in a specific RAN). In fact, both approaches can be combined into a two-stage detection process.

Moreover, our proposal is easily flexible, because of allowing to dynamically deploy new virtualized resources in order to detect anomaly symptoms in a particular RAN when network traffic increases, and also extensible, since the symptom detection, which is the most expensive analysis process, is distributed among RAN, while the anomaly detection is centralized in core network, which is also known as the Evolved Packet Core (EPC), only needs the symptoms as input.

In order to implement both analysis functions, there are several machine learning alternatives, some related to deep learning. However, a key aspect is to identify the network flow features that will be analyzed in order to detect anomaly symptoms. In our proposal, accounting flows is a two-step process: flow exporting and flow collection. The flow exporter, also known as observation point, is responsible for the metering process, i.e., creating flow records from observed traffic. The flow collector is in charge of retrieving and storing the flows created by the flow exporter as well as sending network flow features in a form suitable to the anomaly symptom detection module.

B. Network flow features

A flow export requires a protocol, namely NetFlow that defines how flow records are transported to the flow collector. NetFlow transports flow records that contains source and destination IP addresses and ports, start and end timestamps, type of service, level 3 protocol, TCP flags, next hop router, input and output SNMP interfaces, source and destination autonomous systems and network masks. Moreover, each flow carries aggregated information about the amount of packets and bytes exchanged.

Each flow record could be directly sent from the flow collector to the symptom detection module. However, the flow record is too simple and only allows to extract a few features. A forward step is to obtain aggregated views choosing a set of flow records. In this case, a timer and/or accounting function trigger the aggregation process that extracts features from flow records. Table I shows our proposal of features extracted from a set of flow records.

The number of features is more than several hundreds if aggregation view considers several set of flows, e.g. considering set of flows within each 1-minute and 1-second period. However, the needed features depends on the machine learning technique and type of network anomaly to detect, i.e. finding TCP anomalies (e.g. TCP port scanning) only requires TCP features.

C. Deep learning-based inspection techniques

Many artificial intelligence tasks can be solved by choosing the right representation or set of features, and then providing them to a simple machine learning algorithm. However it is not

easy to know what features should be extracted (this is called the learning representation problem). Deep learning essentially uses the well-known multilayer perceptron to obtain, in a unsupervised way, higher level representations expressed in terms of other simpler ones. Each layer can be seen as another step of a computer program that uses the previous layer's result as input.

Deep learning algorithms have achieved state-of-art results in a range of difficult problem domains, involving supervised and unsupervised learning. Several types of deep learning neural networks can be found: convolutional neural networks, Deep Belief Networks (DBN), Restricted Boltzman Machines (RBM), Long Short-Term Memory Recurrent Networks (LSTM), etc. Each of them is particularly well suited to deal with a different sort of classification problems. Anomaly detection in computer networks has been subject of study for decades, and many approaches have been explored [12], [13] and the deep learning perspective has received special attention in recent years [14].

In our architecture, the anomaly detection is arranged in two levels (Fig. 3). At the low level, the Flow Collector (FC) gets all the different flows during a given period of time, calculates a vector of features that the Anomaly Symptom Detection module (ASD) will classify as anomalous or normal. This initial classification has to be made as fast as possible even sacrificing accuracy. If an anomaly is suspected, a symptom packet composed of the feature vector involved, a time stamp, and the type of anomaly detected, is sent to the next level, the Network Anomaly Detection module (NAD). The NAD receives several streams of symptoms from all the ASDs, sorts them by their time stamps and assembles a time sequence of symptoms. The task of deciding whether this sequence belongs to any of a set of attack categories can be seen as a symptom-sequence classification problem.

Essentially anomaly detection techniques can operate in one of the following three modes [12]:

- Supervised detection: A training set with traffic labeled as normal or anomalous is available.
- Semi-supervised detection: The training set contains only normal traffic, and anything that does not belong to this kind of traffic is considered anomalous.
- Unsupervised detection: No labeled training set is necessary.

In the supervised detection, the main issue is how to build a really comprehensive training set with all the anomalous traffic properly labeled. This can be hard to achieve and harder to maintain. In this case every piece of traffic belonging to one of the defined categories will be correctly classified, but if a new type of traffic anomaly appears, it will be incorrectly classified. In fact the usual technique to obtain a labeled training set consists in injecting anomalous traffic in a normal traffic stream, because this kind of set is not readily available. There are several reasons for this, such as the excessive effort needed to collect that sort of data, the level of expert knowledge that would be necessary for the analysis, or users' privacy issues. Due to this, together with the huge amount of data to

TABLE I
FEATURES EXTRACTED BY NETWORK FLOWS.

Types of flows	Total	Features (t)
TCP/UDP	52/40	number of flows, number of incoming flows, number of outgoing flows fraction of incoming/outgoing flows over total, fraction of symmetric/asymmetric incoming flows sum/max/min/mean/variance/deviation/entropy of packets per incoming/outgoing flows sum/max/min/mean/variance/deviation/entropy of bytes per incoming/outgoing flows entropy of src IP for incoming flows, entropy of src port for incoming flows, entropy of dst ports for incoming flows fraction of dst ports ≤ 1024 for incoming flows, fraction of dst port > 1024 for incoming flows (only TCP) fraction of incoming/outgoing flows with SYN/ACK/URG/FIN/RST/PUSH flag set
ICMP	36	number of flows, number of incoming flows, number of outgoing flows fraction of incoming/outgoing flows over total, fraction of symmetric/asymmetric incoming flows sum/max/min/mean/variance/deviation/entropy of packets per incoming/outgoing flows sum/max/min/mean/variance/deviation/entropy of bytes per incoming/outgoing flows entropy of src IP for incoming flows

Fig. 3. Detail of the low-level (ASD) and high-level (NAD) modules.

be examined to keep this set updated, it is necessary making the training process as independent as possible from the availability of labeled anomalous data. However, when a classifier is tested in a network widely different from the one where training data were taken from, the detection performance drops [15]. Unsupervised anomaly detection methods have been proposed [16] so that the knowledge of traffic behavior on which the model is based can be progressively constructed and dynamically evolve over time. Unfortunately in our case they are not suitable because building and training *in situ* such a self-learning model is a costly process. We are interested in time-effective solutions that offer sufficient accuracy with a low evaluation runtime, in order to process the huge amount of features our architecture needs to manage per second.

Deep Belief Networks (DBN) and Stacked Autoencoders (SAE) are common learning methods which have demonstrated to be effective at learning invariant features from complex and high-dimensional datasets. The Restricted Boltzmann Machine (RBM) is the building block of a DBN [17], where each layer is separately greedily trained as a RBM that takes the input from the feature layer learned in the previous layer. SAE use the same idea to train stacked autoencoders in an unsupervised way, one at a time, to obtain a set of more

descriptive low-dimension features. DBN can be used as is or optionally be fine-tuned by some backpropagation layers in a supervised way [18]. On the other hand, these backpropagation layers are necessary if SAE is going to be used.

In this paper we focus on analyzing the performance of the ASD module. The huge amount of traffic each RAN must support makes it crucial to be able to process a sufficient number of flows per second, even though the detection is not as precise as it could be. With this in mind, it is desirable that the selected machine learning method meets the following requirements:

- It should be suitable for efficient execution on a GPU.
- It should be computed in a constant number of operations for a given feature vector size.
- It should have the same memory requirements regardless of the number of samples used in training.
- It should achieve good accuracy in classification but it does not need to be extremely accurate.

A complex issue is the definition of anomaly. An anomaly is something that appears very infrequently, and is tightly linked to the concept of normality. Essentially we can consider as anomalous all the network traffic that do not match in the

normal class. Consequently anomaly detection system should not be limited by any predefined set of anomalies, and they should be flexible enough to adapt themselves to any unknown event affecting the network.

DBN and SAE has been the chosen models for this preliminary work. They have essentially the same structure and the prediction can be computed using matrix operations. Some authors [16] propose using a Support Vector Machine (SVM) as a final supervised classifier. We have initially avoided using a SVM because the number of support vectors obtained during the training phase depends on the dataset and this can make it difficult to obtain an upper bound of the execution time. Three different depth architectures with one, three and six hidden layers has been selected to be evaluated. The depth necessary depends on whether the architecture can capture the large degree of variation that occurs in the network data. These models are to be previously trained using a training set labeled as *normal* or *anomalous*. If no labeled set is available, we can convert a DBN into a semi-supervised method simply training with the normal network traffic and using the DBN as a sort of RBM without any further backpropagation layer [15]. Even in this case, the matrix operations needed to obtain the prediction are essentially the same.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

There are a significant number of libraries and frameworks related to deep learning that can be used to train our model. They have to be capable of managing LSTM Recurrent Networks (this is the model we have planned to use in our NAD) and DBNs. It must also have GPUs support and allow multi-node parallel execution for future extensions. The ones selected from those which meet the requirements were: Tensorflow [19], Caffe [20], Torch [21], Theano [22], Deeplearning4j [23] and MXNet [24]. All of them have been widely used in all kinds of high performance projects. Researchers are usually interested in the training time of the model because is the more time-consuming part in deep learning. However, we need a framework that also evaluates the trained model as fast as possible due to the time restrictions inherent to our problem. Although it can be argued that such a framework is not strictly necessary to make predictions, we do not want to discard the possibility of having a continuous unsupervised refinement of the deep learning model.

In this preliminary work, Tensorflow's performance has been evaluated by using a DBN model where the *input* layer has the same size as the feature vector, and the output layer size is 2, so that softmax can be used to estimate the likelihood of belonging to the normal or anomalous class. In the future, the output can be extended to match the different potentially detected attacks. The chosen architectures are:

- One hidden full layer of 128 floats
- Three hidden full layers of 128, 64 and 32 floats
- Six hidden full layers of 128, 96, 64, 48, 32 and 16 floats

In order to obtain an upper bound, we have assumed that the batched feature vectors arrive at maximum speed, and that the CPU uses them to evaluate the DBN or to feed the

DBN executed by the GPU, normally by means of a memory copy. Several factors have to be taken into account when we want to reach the best performance. The batch size has great influence on the execution time, regardless of the processor that evaluates the model. If the model is evaluated by the CPU, increasing the batch size will cause more cache/TLB misses and page faults. If the model is evaluated by the GPU, increasing the batch size will decrease the execution time, but will increase the time spent on transferring the batch to the GPU's memory. In this preliminary work we have used only one GPU, so the batch size is limited by the GPU's memory size. Deep learning frameworks usually try to optimize the memory usage; however, they replicate certain structures in some specific models (p.e. CNNs) in order to improve parallelism at the cost of a greater memory usage.

Every layer in the model has a matrix-vector product associated. For example, in the three hidden model, the sizes of the matrices when the input is a 128-element feature vector and the output layer has 2 neurons are 128×128 , 128×64 , 64×32 , and 32×2 float elements.

We carried out the performance evaluation using a workstation with 32GB of RAM, a six-core Intel i7-5930K at 3.5GHz with hyper-threading running Linux, and 1 NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1080 with 8GB RAM using Tensorflow 1.0, CUDA 8.0 and CUDNN 5.1.

A. Determining the optimum batch size

Tensorflow is a software library for numerical computation based on data flow graphs where the nodes represent operations and the edges represent the tensors communicated between them. Its flexible architecture allows you to deploy computation to one or more CPUs or GPUs in a variety of hardware platforms with a single API. We have decided to take it as a black box and to use a benchmark executed during the installation procedure of our software on each ASD. Its execution takes approximately two hours, but it has to be done just once. This allows us to determine the optimum batch size for every given vector size for a wide range of values and the three aforementioned deep-learning model architectures.

For the shake of brevity only the resulting performance for the six hidden layer neural network running on the GPU is shown in Fig. 4. It can be seen that the speedup, as a function of the vector size when the batch size is fixed, is not linear. There might be too many reasons for this fact (memory transfer time, computing time, number of GPU threads, CUDA's grid and block dimensions, among others), and they should be analyzed, but our goal is not to give an insightful description of this behavior, but tuning our software to maximize its performance.

The size of the feature vector depends on the number of features we can obtain and this number is almost limited to our imagination. There are so many potential features [18] that we have fixed our feature vector to 128 elements. With this input vector size and running the models on our workstation, the best batch size in the three neural networks architectures

Fig. 4. Average performance for the most common batch size and feature vector size values when running on the GPU. The largest batch size for each feature vector size is limited by the GPU memory (8GB).

Fig. 5. Comparison between CPU and GPU performance for each of the three DBN architectures.

are $2^{17} = 131\,072$, $2^{15} = 32\,768$ and $2^{15} = 32\,768$ for one, three, and six hidden layers, respectively (Fig. 5).

B. CPU versus GPU performance

Once the feature vector size has been fixed, Fig. 5 shows the number of feature vectors processed per second for a CPU and a GPU with each batch size. GPUs have become an essential tool for machine learning computation. Most deep learning models are really well suited to be executed on a GPU and make the best of it. The more complex and independent the computations, the more impressive the performance gain.

Our model can be considered as not too deep, and the matrices as really small if compared with those typical in other deep learning models (e.g., CNNs). In this case, the time spent to transfer the batch from main memory to the GPU cannot be disregarded and it compensates the greater GPU performance. Fig.5 shows this little performance difference between CPU and GPU in the one-layer architecture. Here the CPU's best performance is 1.83 million feature vectors per second whereas the GPU's best mark was 2.85M. The speedup of CPU versus GPU for large batch sizes is rather small: the speedup ranges from a minimum of 1.28 and a maximum of 1.83.

When the number of layers increases, the gap between CPU and GPU performance increases dramatically. In the six-layer

model, the speedup ranges from a minimum of 2.2 with a batch size of 2^{19} and a maximum of 3,06 with a batch size of 2^{15} . The maximum performance is 2.93 million feature vectors per second.

The GPU performances for the three models are rather similar. This proves that the GPU's 2560 cores have a huge computing power on high parallelizable computations like matrix-vector product, and that the majority of the time is spent in data transfers instead of calculations.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

A novel two-level deep machine learning model has been proposed in the context of a 5G mobile network architecture. The first level is a supervised or semi-supervised learning model implementing a DBN or a SAE running on every RAN as fast as possible. This sacrifices some accuracy, due to the amount of traffic data that a RAN supports. Its task is to detect *symptoms*, that is, local anomalous traffic conditions that happens during a configurable short time period. All the collected symptoms are sent to our NAD, where they are assembled and used as input for a LSTM Recurrent Network trained in a supervised way to recognize temporal patterns of typical attacks.

Several directions for future improvement can be considered. Firstly, in this paper we have only evaluated Tensorflow,

but it would be necessary to make a comprehensive comparative performance evaluation of deep learning frameworks, so as to determine the best suited one for reaching the highest processing performance. We have used only a GPU but we do not know at what extent several GPUs in the same machine could improve the performance. The data are collected by the CPU, so there might be a bottleneck that prevented GPUs from reaching its peak performance. This could allow us to use a more complex first level model if a good GPU load balancing were implemented. Even if a huge amount of data has been used to train a deep learning model, the traffic patterns may change and it would be necessary to update or retrain our model. To manage this problem, it would be necessary to find out the most adequate way of keep our model fitted. This can be done by using a unsupervised symptom detector or fine-tuning a supervised one with new network flows representative of the class of anomaly to detect. And finally, it is necessary to train the two different levels using real data and evaluate the accuracy of the anomaly detection architecture as a whole.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work has been supported by the European Commission Horizon 2020 Programme under grant agreement number H2020-ICT-2014-2/671672 - SELFNET (*Framework for Self-Organized Network Management in Virtualized and Software Defined Networks*), the Spanish MINECO (project DHARMA, *Dynamic Heterogeneous Threats Risk Management and Assessment*, with code TIN2014-59023-C2-1-R; and project TecMASAS, *Techniques to Improve the Architecture of Servers, Applications and Services*, with code TIN2015-66972-C5-3-R), and the European Commission (FEDER/ERDF).

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